

Mesoporous bioactive glass doped with therapeutic inorganic ions

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ABSTRACT

In the present study the mesoporous bioactive glass (MBG) particles were prepared by microemulsion assisted sol-gel technique. Incorporation of therapeutic inorganic ions (TII) enhance the biological impact of MBG materials. Metallic ions such as strontium, copper, gallium, cerium, magnesium and boron have been incorporated to the binary system SiO₂ / CaO with the nominal composition of 60/40 mol %. The effect of TII doping on the morphology and chemical composition of MBG nanoparticles was investigated. Using the microemulsion assisted sol-gel preparation technique the influence of Sr²⁺, B³⁺, Mg²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ga³⁺ and Ce³⁺ dopants on the morphology and chemical composition has been studied. The used dopants have a significant effect on the size, shape and chemical composition when the conditions of the sol-gel process are fixed. The presented results will help to understand better the effect of therapeutic inorganic ions incorporation into the bioactive glasses, in aim to fully reveal their potential in the field of biomedical applications such as bone, soft tissue engineering, drug loading, etc.

Keywords: sol-gel, mesoporous bioactive glass, therapeutic ions, morphology, bioactivity

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